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**ASSESSING THE IMPACTS OF LAND USE CHANGES ON TREE OCCURRENCE
AND DIVERSITY**

**A CASE STUDY: NALWENKOMBA WETLAND CATCHMENT IN NAMASAGALI
SUBCOUNTY, KAMULI DISTRICT IN EASTERN UGANDA**

BY

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**Research Project submitted to the Faculty of Natural Resources and Environmental
Sciences in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree in Natural
Resource Economics**

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DECLARATION

I, Odongo Ivan, declare that this research titled "*Assessing the Impacts of Land Use and Land Cover Changes on Tree Occurrence and Diversity in Nwekomba Wetland Catchment Area in Kamuli District, Uganda*" is my original work. It is the culmination of my efforts and contributions, conducted under the guidance and supervision of Professor Isabirye Moses towards the completion of my bachelor of science in Natural Resource Economics.

SIGNATURE:

DATE.....

ODONGO IVAN

APPROVAL

This is to certify that the research titled "Assessing Impacts of Land Use and Land Cover Changes on Tree Occurrence and Diversity in Nalwekomba Wetland Catchment Area in Kamuli District, Uganda" by Odongo Ivan has been examined and approved by the undersigned by Professor Isabirye Moses and the head of department Natural Resource Economics, Faculty of Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences. The research has been reviewed and found acceptable for submission in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the bachelors of science in Natural Resource Economics.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this research work to:

- My Family Members especially my parents Mr. Ngolobe Patrick and Mrs. Nandera Everlyne together with my elder sisters including Ms. Auma Leticia, Ms. Apio Mary Rayantah (my twin sister) and my little ones (Kizza Aldrine, Vanessa Nakamya, and Nabwire Vivian Mary) whose unwavering support, prayers, and encouragement have been my guiding light throughout this journey.
- Professor Isabirye Moses (Busitema University, Research Supervisor), Prof. Wilson Waiswa Mwanja, JBN Consults & Planners Ltd, Mrs. Ariango Esther, Ms. Nanteza Aisha (MSc. Geo-information science and technology Makerere University), Mr. Musobya Moses (researcher and lecturer, NaFIRRI & Busitema University)
- The resilient community of Nalwekomba Wetland Catchment Area in Kamuli District, whose cooperation and insights have enriched this research and its findings.

Your love, guidance, encouragement, and understanding have been instrumental in shaping this endeavor. This work stands as a tribute to your support and the inspiration drawn from your experiences.

Above all, I give glory and honor back to God who has gifted me with His spirit and life amidst my trials during my research up to now.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

NRE	Natural Resource Economics
FWR	Fisheries and Water Resource Management
BSc.	Bachelor of science
LULC	Land use land cover
NaFIRRI	National Fisheries Resource Research Institute
TOD	Tree Occurrence and Diversity
FPIC	Free Prior and Informed Consent
Ugshs.	Uganda Shillings
MSc.	Masters of Science
Prof.	Profesor
Ha	Hectares
Yr.	Year
USGS	United States Geological Survey
UNCCD	United Nation Convention for Combating Desertification

ABSTRACT

This research examines the profound influence of land use and land cover changes on tree occurrence and diversity within the Nalwenkomba Wetland Catchment in Uganda's Kamuli District. Employing a mixed-methods approach encompassing remote sensing, vegetation surveys, and socioeconomic analysis, the study scrutinized the years 2013 to 2021. The findings revealed that among the catchment's 216.25 square kilometers, 20.83% experienced degradation, while 17.09% showed improvement, and 62.08% remained stable based on land condition assessments. The degraded land witnessed substantial alterations due to deforestation (for timber, charcoal, and firewood), agricultural expansion (notably sugarcane farming), and artificial urbanization activities like construction and sand mining, resulting in an annual degradation of 563.86 hectares.

This degradation has negatively impacted tree occurrence and diversity, influencing habitat structure and environmental conditions within the catchment, home to over 26 tree species. Notably, transitions towards agroforestry systems, particularly cropland to agroforestry, emerged as potential solutions to enhance tree occurrence and species diversity. These changes not only boosted tree numbers and species but also improved soil fertility, water retention, and overall ecosystem services.

Community involvement emerged as pivotal, with 84% of the sampled households actively engaged in conservation efforts, underscoring the significance of local knowledge and participation in sustainable land management practices. Conversely, the conversion of land from agroforestry to specific croplands, especially sugarcane fields, significantly diminished tree occurrence and diversity.

This study significantly augments existing knowledge by offering detailed insights into how land use changes impact tree occurrence and diversity within wetland catchments. It emphasizes the importance of adopting sustainable practices, particularly agroforestry, and highlights the indispensable role of community engagement in preserving tree diversity amidst evolving land use patterns. Ultimately, it underscores the need for informed land management strategies to maintain and enhance tree diversity, crucial for the resilience and functionality of ecosystems within these delicate environments.

Keywords: Land use changes, Tree occurrence, Tree diversity, Wetland catchment, Sustainable land management, Agroforestry.

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Wetlands represent some of the world's most diverse and ecologically significant ecosystems, providing invaluable services such as water purification, flood control, and habitat for a multitude of plant and animal species (*Mitsch and Gosselink, 2015*). Among these ecosystems, wetland catchments are particularly crucial, offering essential ecological functions. Tree diversity within wetland catchments plays a central role in shaping these ecosystems, influencing hydrological processes, nutrient cycling, and providing habitats for a myriad of species. These areas are, however, increasingly vulnerable to land use and land cover changes, primarily driven by human activities (*Denny et al., 2017*).

In Uganda, literature mention that small wetlands make up more than 5-7% of Uganda's total wetland area (*Sakané et al., 2011*) and (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). The Kamuli district is home to the Nalwekomba wetland Catchment, a significant wetland catchment area known for its ecological importance. A recent related research paper discovered that the impacts of LULCC are site specific and included a reduction of: tree cover and species composition; water quality and quantity; and soil quality (*Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020*). The same research indicates statistics that how forest cover in Uganda decreased in area from 49,334 km² from 1990 to 36,655 km² in 2005 (*Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020*). This was a significant impact on tree species diversity and occurrence especially in local areas and thus imperative to protection. Wetland catchments have long served as a vital component of the local environment, contributing to the well-being of both the ecosystem and the communities residing within its vicinity such as habitat for various tree diversity including *Muvule, Musizi, Gacia*, etc. lessening flooding and its impacts, potential source of water for locals. However, the Nalwekomba wetland, like many other wetlands globally, faces substantial anthropogenic pressures. LULC change activities such as deforestation, agricultural expansion especially sugarcane growing (*Alice Nakiyemba, 2021*), sand extraction, charcoal burning, and settlement development are gradually reshaping the landscape of this wetland catchment. The occurrence and diversity of various tree species in the wetland catchment has a number of ecological, and economical importance. Trees contribute to the stability and enhancement of the catchment hydrology regimes thus lessening floods, trees provide protection from heavy storms and winds, source of medicine, habitat for multiple animal and bird species. The LULC changes have the potential to exert a profound influence on tree diversity and occurrence within Nalwekomba, thereby impacting the broader

ecosystem services it provides (*Pullanikkatil, 2016*), (*Houlahan, 2003*), (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*) (*Alice Nakiyemba, 2021*), (*Bennett, 2015*) and (*Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020*).

This research aims to address the knowledge gap surrounding the intricate relationships between land use land cover change and tree diversity in wetland catchments, using the Nalwekomba wetland as a case study. By conducting a comprehensive assessment of these impacts on tree diversity and occurrence, this study seeks to contribute to the understanding of the dynamics within wetland catchment including the hydrology and the changes in land use and land cover, aid in the development of informed conservation and management strategies, and underscore the significance of preserving tree diversity within these ecosystems.

1.2. Main objective

To assess the impact of LULC on above ground biodiversity condition with focus on tree occurrence and diversity.

1.2.1. Specific objectives

- i. To detect land use change and Land cover in the Nalwekomba Wetland Catchment.
- ii. To determine the tree occurrence and diversity.
- iii. To assess the LULC impacts on tree occurrence and diversity.

1.3. Research Questions

- i. What are the LULC in the study area?
- ii. What is the tree occurrence and diversity in the Nalwekomba wetland catchment?
- iii. What are the impacts of LULC on the tree occurrence and diversity in the study area?

1.4. Problem statement

Wetland catchments are ecologically significant areas, crucial for providing water regulation, carbon sequestration, and habitat provision. However, they are increasingly vulnerable to the impacts of Land Use Land Cover (LULC) change, driven by urbanization, agriculture, and infrastructure development (*Turner, 2015*) and (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). Uganda lost on average 122,000 ha/year of forest between the years 1990 and 2015, in favour of agricultural area expansion (*Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020*). LULC changes can lead to shifts in habitat structure and environmental conditions, potentially affecting tree diversity and occurrence within these ecosystems (*Houlahan, 2003*), (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*), and (*Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020*). Alteration of the catchment hydrology regimes attributed to human activities like tree cutting,

mining, sugarcane and rice growing in the catchment has resulted into flooding that recently destroyed lives and property of locals in Kamuli (*Daily Monitor, 2020*). While recognized studies such as (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*) research provided insights into the delineation of the Nalwekomba wetland and predicted future land cover changes in the catchment, there remains a lack of comprehensive research on the specific consequences of LULC change on tree communities in these ecosystems.

This study aims to address the research gap by evaluating the impacts of LULC change on tree diversity and occurrence in wetland catchments. It involved use of remote sensing, field surveys, and data analysis, this research intends to quantify LULC changes and evaluate their effects on tree populations within wetland catchments. Additionally, this study considered mediating factors like hydrological alterations which and climate change, which may interact with LULC change to influence tree diversity.

Understanding the impacts of LULC change on tree diversity and occurrence in wetland catchments is vital, given the critical role of these ecosystems in environmental stability and biodiversity conservation (*Ramsar Convention, 2016*). The expected outcomes of this study include quantifiable data on the extent and nature of LULC change and its consequences for tree communities. By addressing this research problem, the study seeks to contribute to the sustainable management and protection of these ecosystems and their tree populations amid ongoing environmental transformations.

1.5 Conceptual framework

The framework identifies land use and land cover changes (LULCC) as the primary drivers of change, encompassing human activities such as deforestation and urbanization. These changes, in turn, are mediated by hydrological and climatic factors, as well as community and conservation efforts. The framework hypothesizes that increasing LULCC negatively affects tree diversity but suggests that mediating factors like hydrological conditions can moderate this impact. It also highlights the significant role of community engagement and conservation in preserving tree diversity. This conceptual framework serves as a guide for the research, emphasizing the complex web of interactions that shape the tree diversity and occurrence in the Nalwekomba wetland within the context of anthropogenic change.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant for several reasons. First, it contributes to the understanding of how human-induced land use and land cover changes affect tree diversity in wetland catchments, which are vital for biodiversity conservation. Second, the findings provided valuable insights for policymakers, land managers, and conservationists in the Kamuli district and beyond, aiding in the development of effective conservation and land management strategies. Additionally, this research could serve as a model for assessing the impacts of land use and land cover change on tree diversity in other wetland catchments globally.

1.7 Scope of the study

This research focuses on the Nalwekomba wetland in the Kamuli district in Eastern Uganda. The study encompassed historical land use and land cover change detection, current tree diversity, and the relationships between these factors. Field surveys, remote sensing data, and geographic information systems (GIS) and Remote sensing was employed to gather data. The study considered all tree species found within the wetland catchment area.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Tree diversity and occurrence in wetland ecosystems are critical components of biodiversity and ecosystem stability. Understanding the drivers that influence the distribution and abundance of tree species within wetlands is essential for effective conservation and management. Several key drivers have been identified in the scientific literature that impact tree diversity and occurrence (*Mereta, 2012*). Land use and land cover changes, including deforestation, agriculture, urbanization, and human activities, have been identified as primary drivers affecting tree populations within wetlands (*Pullanikkatil, 2016*), (*Bai, Y., Wu, J., & Xing, Q, 2008*) and wetland catchments (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). The conversion of wetland areas for agricultural (*Alice Nakiyemba, 2021*) use and urban expansion often leads to habitat loss and fragmentation, which, in turn, can significantly alter tree species composition and distribution (*Schmiegelow, 2002*) and (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*)

2.2. The LULC change detection

The LULC of study area, Nalwekomba wetland catchment was recently analysed using by (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*) in her recent research and the catchment was classified into six LULC classes including

2.2.1. LULC Changes in Wetland Catchments and TOD

The accelerated pace of urbanization and agricultural expansion has led to considerable LULC changes within and around wetland catchments (*Song, Kaishan and Wang, Zongming and Li, Lin and Tedesco, Lenore and Li, Fang and Jin, Cui and Du, Jia, 2012*) and (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). These changes often entail the conversion of natural land cover into built-up areas, croplands, and transportation networks (*Mitsch and Gosselink, 2015*) and (*Thonfeld, 2020*). Such modifications can result in complex and interconnected effects on tree diversity within these ecosystems (*Bai, Y., Wu, J., & Xing, Q, 2008*).

According to (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*), the vegetation in Nalwekomba wetland catchment consists of degraded forest with encroaching rice, sugarcane and subsistence farms, human settlements, and converted to arable land. Road constructions through the wetland have resulted in major alterations in some areas of the wetland. Fishing, raw materials (sand) mining for construction work, and cattle rearing are other major livelihood activities in the wetland. (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*) also described Nalwekomba wetland catchment to have a tropical

climate characterised by two rain seasons is experienced in the study area, with peaks in March – June and August – November that synchronise with the wetland’s bimodal flooding regimes. The average annual rainfall is 1,350mm with a mean monthly rainfall of 75 mm to 259 mm, monthly mean surface air temperatures of 24°C with minimum and maximum ranges of 14 to 19 ° C and 28 to 36 ° C, respectively (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). However, this is being altered by so many factors not limited to climate change and human activities in the area.

Therefore, entire dynamic composition of the wetland catchment ecosystem interplay with human activities to hence influence the diversity and occurrence of trees in the study area.

2.2 Hydrological and Climatic Factors

Apart from anthropogenic drivers, hydrological changes and climatic variability also play a vital role in shaping tree diversity and occurrence in wetland catchments. Hydrological alterations, such as changes in water levels and flooding patterns, can have profound effects on tree species composition. Wetland ecosystems are especially sensitive to variations in hydrological regimes, and shifts in these patterns can influence the distribution of species adapted to specific moisture conditions. Additionally, climate variability, including changes in temperature and precipitation, affects tree growth and the range of certain species. These climatic factors can contribute to the expansion or contraction of tree populations within wetlands (*Asselen, 2013*).

2.3. Wetland Catchments

Wetland catchment areas are integral components of global ecosystems, providing a multitude of ecological services, including water regulation, carbon sequestration, and habitat provision (*Mitsch and Gosselink, 2015*). The richness of tree species within these ecosystems contributes significantly to their ecological functioning and biodiversity. However, the sustainability of wetland catchments is increasingly threatened by Land Use Land Cover (LULC) changes resulting from urbanization, agriculture, and infrastructure development (*Turner, 2015*). These LULC changes can significantly alter habitat structure and environmental conditions, subsequently affecting tree diversity and occurrence. A catchment is an area that a river or a lake gets its water from. In the wetland context, wetlands are dependent on the catchments. According to (*Tom Baker, and Edward Maltby, 2009*) (book editors) “The Wetlands Handbook” page 660-661 explained that, subtle hydrological changes can consequently have significant impacts for ecological character, biodiversity and the processes that result in the products, functions and attributes that make wetlands valuable. The hydrological change may originate

from alterations to climate, changes in catchment land use, management or ground water abstraction. Tom Bakers and Edward book “The wetlands Handbook” also says that these land uses are mostly driven by demographic pressure, agriculture and urbanisation. Wetlands thus have significant controls on hydrology thus any management strategies require an integrated catchment approach.

Table 1. A range of wetland functions services especially global diversity normally provided by wetland ecosystems. the provision of ecosystem services on wetland functioning, which is itself dependent on the operation of natural wetland process. (extracted from (Tom Baker, and Edward Maltby, 2009))

Wetland process	Wetland function	Service provision
Ecological: provision of overall structural diversity, provision of microsites for: macroinvertebrates Fish Herptiles Birds Mammals Provision of plant and habitat diversity, biomass production	Ecosystem maintenance	The physical, chemical, and biological processes occurring in wetlands all contribute to the provision of unique habitats, which support a variety of adapted organisms. This contributes to global diversity, and supports recreation and quality of life

2.4. The Importance of Wetland Catchments

Wetland catchments represent vital habitats with unique characteristics and ecological roles. They serve as nurseries for a variety of aquatic organisms, act as water purification systems, and offer refuge and feeding grounds for numerous species (Mitsch and Gosselink, 2015). Additionally, they play a pivotal role in global carbon cycling and act as sinks for greenhouse gases, thus contributing to climate change mitigation (Davidson, 2014). The tree populations within wetland catchments are instrumental in maintaining the health and resilience of these ecosystems. They provide stability to the soil, contribute to nutrient cycling, and offer habitat for diverse wildlife (Fennessy et al., 2007). Wetlands rely on water from the surrounding catchment and therefore can only be managed effectively through taking a catchment

perspective which requires a catchment management plan that includes sufficient allocation of wetlands. Tree diversity in wetland catchments is not only ecologically significant but also economically important, contributing to the livelihoods of local communities through various forest products (*Hett and Loucks, 1976*).

2.5. Human Activities

Human activities causing the LULC changes have a profound impact on tree diversity and occurrence in wetland catchments (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*) and (*Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020*). These diverse ecosystems, which are critical for biodiversity and ecosystem services, face a range of anthropogenic pressures that can result in alterations to the composition and distribution of tree species (*Turner et al., 2007; Bai, Y., Wu, J., & Xing, Q, 2008*). Deforestation, urbanization, agriculture (e.g. Sugarcane growing (*Alice Nakiyemba, 2021*)), sand extraction, and other land use changes have been identified as key human activities affecting wetland tree populations (*Dwire & Kauffman, 2003*), (*Alice Nakiyemba, 2021*) and (*Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020*). Nalwekomba wetland catchment in particular is greatly facing increased build-up areas/settlement and cropland and these changes are affecting tree cover according to the recent research by (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). Gimbo's research results indicated that The LULC prediction results had a high percentage expansions expected for built-up & settlement of 71.9 %, open water 8.4%, and cropland 15.4 %; and major percentage reductions for tree cover by 22.47%, grassland by 4.6% and shrubland by 3.88% (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*).

2.5.1. Deforestation

Deforestation is one of the most significant human activities affecting wetland tree diversity. Forested wetlands play a crucial role in maintaining a diverse range of tree species (*Dwire & Kauffman, 2003*). However, deforestation driven by timber extraction, land conversion, and infrastructure development often leads to habitat loss, fragmentation, and shifts in the composition of tree communities (*Ghermandi, 2010*).

Figure 2. First photo of “Mutuba” tree cut for Timber, firewood and charcoal production in the catchment area

Most of these human activities were discovered happening in Nalwekomba catchment area by (Gimbo R et al., 2023) as she described the state of the catchment.

Figure 3. Second photo of “Mutuba” tree cut for Timber, firewood and charcoal production in the catchment area

Research has shown that these changes can negatively impact the occurrence of native tree species adapted to wetland conditions, while simultaneously creating opportunities for invasive species (Gaston, 2000).

2.5.1. Agriculture

Agriculture, particularly in the form of wetland conversion for cultivation, is another substantial driver of tree diversity and occurrence changes in catchment areas. In the Nalwekomba catchment, a research by (Alice Nakiyemba, 2021) indicated that sugarcane growing as the main cause of Nalwekomba wetland degradation which consists of completely clearing of trees for sugarcane growing. As wetlands are drained and transformed into agricultural fields, the hydrological conditions are altered (Camacho-Valdez, 2014). This, in turn, influences the types of tree species that can thrive in the modified environment. Research indicates that certain tree species may be lost as a result of these changes, while others, better suited to drier conditions, may encroach upon the former wetland areas (Ghermandi & van den Bergh, 2007; Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020; Gimbo. R et al., 2023).

2.5.2. Urbanization, Sand Extraction, and Other Human Activities

Urbanization and sand extraction activities within wetland catchments have been dominant in Nalwekomba wetland impacts on tree diversity and occurrence. Urban expansion leads to the destruction of wetland habitat, causing loss and displacement of tree species adapted to these environments (Turner et al., 2007).

Sand extraction can directly alter wetland topography, potentially leading to the loss of riparian and wetland trees (Bai, Y., Wu, J., & Xing, Q, 2008)

Figure 4. below showing Sand mining in the catchment

Additionally, various other human activities, such as infrastructure development, also contribute to the alteration of tree diversity and occurrence in wetland catchment.

2.6. Climate Change

Climate change is increasingly recognized as a major driver of shifts in tree diversity and occurrence in wetland catchments. Wetlands are sensitive ecosystems that are highly influenced by changes in temperature, precipitation patterns, and extreme weather events (Breshears et al., 2008). This was related the recent flooding in Kamuli catchment area according to (Daily Monitor, 2020) and the Nalwekomba recent flooding of year 2023 that lasted for over a month more than usual (observation from the field). As the climate continues to warm and become more variable, the impacts on tree species in wetlands can be significant (Allen et al., 2010).

2.6.1. Temperature and Precipitation Changes

One of the primary ways climate change affects tree diversity and occurrence in wetlands is through alterations in temperature and precipitation patterns. Rising temperatures can lead to changes in the growing conditions for tree species, influencing their distribution (Anderegg et al., 2012). In some cases, higher temperatures may benefit certain tree species that are more thermally tolerant, leading to their increased occurrence within wetlands (Cahill et al., 2014). On the other hand, reduced or altered precipitation patterns may negatively impact the availability of water for some tree species, leading to declines in their numbers (Dobrowski et al., 2013).

2.7. Impacts of LULC Changes on Tree Diversity

2.7.1 Alteration of Habitat Structure

Changes in land use, particularly urbanization, can lead to habitat fragmentation, reduced tree cover, and alterations in soil properties (*Liu et al., 2016*). These alterations in habitat structure can influence the composition and distribution of tree species, favoring some while adversely affecting others.

2.7.2 Modification of Environmental Conditions

LULC changes can lead to shifts in microclimatic conditions, including temperature and moisture levels (*Grimm et al., 2008*). Such changes can impact the distribution of tree species with specific environmental requirements. For instance, tree species sensitive to urban heat islands may experience reduced occurrence in areas subjected to urbanization.

2.7.3 Indirect Effects on Tree Communities

LULC changes can have indirect effects on tree communities through alterations in hydrological regimes, such as changes in water flow patterns and sediment deposition (*Liu et al., 2016*). These changes can influence the availability of suitable sites for tree establishment and growth.

2.8. The Role of Local Communities and Conservation Efforts

Understanding the impacts of human activities on tree diversity and occurrence in wetland catchments is crucial for effective conservation and management efforts (*Turner, 2015*). Research in this field not only highlights the threats posed by these activities but also underscores the importance of developing sustainable land use practices and conservation strategies that aim to mitigate the negative impacts and ensure the long-term survival of diverse tree populations in these critical ecosystems (*Loreau, M., & de Mazancourt, C, 2013*). Collaborative efforts involving researchers, local communities, and policymakers are vital in achieving these conservation goals.

Local communities and conservation efforts also exert a significant influence on tree diversity and occurrence in wetland catchments. Traditional ecological knowledge and sustainable land management practices of local communities can contribute to the conservation of tree species in especially the study area. This is because of increased agroforestry where trees such as bamboo, mvule, Musizi have been grown by the locals in especially Namasagali sub county part of the catchment despite the increases built-up and Agriculture in the catchment as discovered by (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). At the same time, the presence of effective conservation initiatives and regulations aimed at preserving wetland ecosystems can shape the protection and restoration of tree diversity which is part of Kamuli District Development Plan. This involved local leaders like district counsellors, and chairperson LC5 of the villages within the catchment area. Collaborative efforts between researchers, government agencies, and community stakeholders can enhance conservation strategies and help mitigate the negative impacts of various drivers on tree diversity in wetland ecosystems. Understanding these drivers and their interactions is crucial for formulating effective conservation and management plans that aim to preserve the ecological and cultural values of wetland trees.

2.9. Knowledge Gaps and Research Needs.

While there is a substantial body of research on wetland ecology and the impacts of LULC changes especially the most recent and relevant study by (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023; Bai, Y., Wu, J., & Xing, Q, 2008; Camacho-Valdez, 2014; Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020*), there is a notable research gap concerning the specific impacts on tree diversity within wetland Catchments, especially in the context of the similar study area with (*Gimbo R et al., 2023*), Nalwekomba wetland in Kamuli district, Uganda. This study seeks to address this gap by conducting a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between land use and land cover changes and tree diversity in the Nalwekomba wetland Catchment.

The following chapters, presents the research methodology, data analysis, and findings of the study, which aims to provide valuable insights into the impacts of land use and land cover change on tree diversity and occurrence in the Nalwekomba wetland Catchment.

2.9.1. Conclusion

This literature review has highlighted the importance of (wetland) catchments and the impacts of LULC changes on the ecosystem services they provide especially of TOD (*Bai, Y., Wu, J., & Xing, Q, 2008; Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). The case study of Nalwekomba Wetland catchment in Namasagali Sub County Kamuli District, Eastern Uganda, is of particular interest due to its vital ecological and socioeconomic importance at local, national and global context and the need for effective management and conservation measures of the wetland catchments and their TOD. Understanding the relationship between LULC changes, and tree diversity and occurrence is crucial for developing sustainable land use practices and ensuring the long-term viability of the wetland catchment ecosystems in Uganda and elsewhere in the world.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the methodology employed to assess the impacts of LULC changes on the **TOD** in Nalwekomba Wetland, Kamuli District in Eastern Uganda. The chapter outlines the research design, data collection methods, analytical techniques, and ethical considerations utilized in the study.

3.2 Study area.

The study area was conducted within the Namasagali catchment which covers a total area of 216.248006 Km² but was approximated to be 216.4 Km² (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). It lies 60 km north of Jinja town; with other districts like Kayunga in the west; Luuka in the South, Buyende on the north-east, and Lake Kyoga in the north (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*). The catchment consists of Namasagali (source of the pour point), Kisaikye Kasozi, Naluwoli, Bugeywa, Butansi, Mbulamuti, Naibowa, Busota, Kisoigo, Namunyigi, Namaira, Namisambyali, and Nakunyalu Parishes. According to (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*), the average annual rainfall of the catchment is 1,350mm with a mean monthly rainfall of 75 mm - 259 mm, mean (monthly) surface air temperatures of 24°C with minimum and maximum ranges of 14- 19 ° C and 28- 36 ° C, respectively. The main focused study area is the part of Nalwekomba wetland catchment where significant LULC changes.

Figure 5. The Map showing the study area, Nalwekomba wetland Catchment in Kamuli District, Eastern Uganda.

3.3 Research Design.

A combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches was employed in this study to comprehensively evaluate the changes in land use and their effects on tree occurrence and diversity. The research design adopted a case study and descriptive approach focusing specifically on Nalwekomba Wetland catchment, providing a comprehensive and an in-depth understanding of the local context.

3.4 Sample size and selection

The sampling size consisted of all areas covered by the Nalwekomba wetland catchment including the Sub Counties of Namasagali, Kisaikye, Kasozi, Naluwoli, Bugeywa, Butansi, Mbulamuti, Naibowa, Busota, Kisoigo, Namunyigi, Namaira, Namisambyali, and Nakunyalu. A total sample size of 60 households to be interviewed were systematically selected from areas

where significant LULC changes (Land Conditions: Improved, Stable and Degraded) had occurred with respect to their degree of impact on tree occurrence and diversity.

Figure 6. Satellite Map (with yellow pins) showing the distribution of selected study sites where LULC changes of interest have occurred.

3.5 Data types and sources

The main source of data was primary data which was provided by myself (researcher and a 3yr resident of the study area through field surveys) and supplemented by respondents who were typical local residents of the area (over 10 years of stay) equipped with indigenous knowledge, experts like ecologists and botanists (offsite/online), and on-site data especially ground truthing data that I gathered with the locals. Secondary data was obtained for purposes of image classification (Landsat 8 images from **USGS**) and remote sensing. This provided precise and original information for reliable results and findings.

3.6 Data Collection methods

Data from respondents was collected with the aid of Kobo toolbox loaded with the questionnaire used in field data collection. Landsat 8 images from 2013 and 2021 and with intervals 8 years with less than 1% cloud cover were downloaded from from the United States Geological Survey (**USGS**). Remote sensing was used in areas where physical exposure to the

environments were impossible, such as very bushy and flooded swamps in the wetland (Turner, W. R, Free, C. M, & Gerrard, R. A, 2014).

Tree inventory was made by myself (section 3.5 during field surveys) with aid of other key informed locals (with indigenous knowledge about the numerous tree species local names). Therefore, most of the tree species names were a mixture of formally known species names and local names.

3.7 Detection of Land Use and Land Cover Change

3.7.1 Remote Sensing Data

Historical satellite imagery from Landsat 8 spanning the past 8 years was used to detect changes in LULC from 2013 to 2021 (8-year interval) and were obtained from USGS were used because they were free to access, available for download. The satellite image used were had a resolution of 30m with less than 1% cloud cover which improved the quality of the final classification.

Table 2. Showing the properties of the satellite images used in LULC classification

Properties of the satellite images used in the classification

Resolution	30m
Cloud Cover	< 1%
Year taken	2013 and 2021 respectively
Month taken	December (for both Landsat imageries)
Source	USGS

This data was analyzed using ArcGIS software to identify alterations in the Nalwekomba catchment area 8 years. This was through a process known as image classification (both classified and unsupervised). However, a non-supervised classification was considered in this case due to the mixed LULC in the catchment. Six (6) different classes were obtained using water, agroforestry, cropland, artificial, swamp and flooded vegetation (later combined with swamp and generalized to “Swamp”). Remote sensing in was used in studies such as (Gimbo. R et al., 2023; Turner, W. R, Free, C. M, & Gerrard, R. A, 2014)

3.8 Current Tree Diversity and Species Occurrence

3.8.1 Vegetation Surveys

Field surveys were conducted to identify and record tree species present in the wetland catchment area by both physical and remote sensing approaches. Surveys covered a representative sample of the wetland area while remote sensing covered the entire catchment, and data on species composition, abundance, and distribution was collected to be used later in the Shannon's diversity index calculations.

3.8.2.1 Mapping and Geospatial Data

ArcGIS of 10.8 version together with google earth pro were utilized (remote sensing) to map the spatial distribution of tree land cover within the different sites of study area. This allowed for the creation of a comprehensive spatial database that integrated tree species and abundance data with relevant environmental variables. The integration of geospatial data was crucial for spatial analyses and the identification of spatial patterns in tree distribution.

3.8.2.2 Socioeconomic Surveys

To gain insight into the socioeconomic factors contributing to LULC changes, structured interviews and questionnaires (from kobo toolbox) were administered to specific local communities and land users where significant LULC changes occurred in the vicinity of the Nalwekomba wetland catchment. Key topics covered in these surveys included: knowledge on LULC changes of the area, tree occurrence and diversity and conservation and management practices.

3.9 Data analysis

3.9.1 Detection of Land Use and Land Cover Change

Remote sensing data was processed and analyzed using ArcGIS (10.8 version) software. Changes in land cover were classified into six classes which were later reclassified. Six classes classified included Agroforestry, Cropland, water, Artificial, Swamp and Flooded vegetation. However, “Swamp” and “flooded vegetation” were combined as one land cover after reclassification. This was because of the mixed LULC of the entire catchment area, e.g., artificial was found to be mixed with agroforestry and cropland in swamps. Temporal trends and patterns of LULC change were identified, and spatial analysis was used to determine the

extent and locations (specific sites) with significant LULC changes that had a substantial impact on tree occurrence and diversity in Nalwekomba wetland area.

3.9.2 Delineation of the wetland catchment

This was used by ArcGIS software version 10.8 and almost in a way congruent to (*Gimbo. R et al., 2023*) as Nalwekomba catchment was done in that paper. However, the pour point might slightly vary due to position point/location. However, for Nalwekomba wetland catchment, if there exists any inaccuracy, its regarded negligible and does not affect the final catchment delineated.

3.9.2 Current Tree Diversity and Species Occurrence

Data collected from field surveys was analysed to determine tree species richness, diversity indices, and species composition within the Nalwekomba wetland Catchment. Statistical analysis, such as species count graphs and Shannon's diversity index, were used to quantify tree diversity. Spatial analysis was used to identify distribution patterns of tree species occurrence in the sample sites. Also, the total number of tree species within the study area was calculated. This indicator provided a fundamental measure of species diversity. The **TOD** was found dependent on different LULC changes in the catchment area.

3.9.2.1. Impact assessment of LULC change on tree TOD

I based on a numbers of methods to assess the impacts of LULC changes on tree occurrence and diversity including the Shannon's tree index, land conditions that included: improved, degraded and stable according to **UNCCD**

3.9.2.2 Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index

The Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index to account for both species' richness and abundance. This index quantified species evenness and considered the uncertainty in predicting the species of a randomly selected individual. The formular is given by:

$$D = \sum i = \frac{1}{R} \ln \left(\frac{N(N-1)}{ni(ni-1)} \right)$$

Where ni is the number of individuals in species i , and N is the total number of species in the sample. An equivalent formula is: $D = \sum i = \frac{1}{R} \ln \frac{1}{pi}$ where pi is the proportional abundance for each species and R is the total number of species in the sample.

3.9.2.2.1 Simpson's Diversity Index

Simpson's index is a weighted arithmetic mean of proportional abundance and measures the probability that two individuals randomly selected from a sample will belong to the same species. Since the mean of the proportional abundance of the species increases with decreasing number of species and increasing abundance of the most abundant species, the value of ***D*** obtains small values in data sets of high diversity and large values in data sets with low diversity. The value of Simpson's ***D*** ranges from **0** to **1**, with **0** representing infinite diversity and **1** representing no diversity, so the larger the value of ***D***, the lower the diversity.

3.9.3. Statistical Analysis

Detailed statistical software especially Microsoft Excel (and Kobo toolbox which supplemented as a guide) was employed for data analysis, in combination with the Shannon's index to explore relationships between diversity indicators and environmental factors.

3.9.4 Socioeconomic Surveys

Data from socioeconomic surveys was subjected to qualitative and quantitative analysis. Qualitative data was thematically analyzed to extract key themes and insights, while quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize responses and identify trends.

3.9.5 Sampling Design and Replication

The sampling design used a systematic approach within the wetland catchment area to study Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) changes. Plots measuring 50m by 50m were systematically selected across different land conditions (Improved, stable, and degraded) within the entire catchment area where LULC changes were observed. The land conditions were imperative to aid in assessing the impacts of LULC changes on tree diversity and occurrence. This method ensured comprehensive coverage while accounting for variability in land conditions. For areas exhibiting minor/small area LULC changes, a complete tree inventory was conducted instead of using plots, allowing for a detailed assessment of tree presence in those specific locations. The inclusion of the three 50m by 50m plots aimed to enhance the reliability and robustness of the study results by capturing variations across the different land conditions.

3.9.6 Data Validation and Quality Control

The accuracy of tree identification was ensured through rigorous quality control measures that included data replication and even distribution of sampling plots through the wetland catchment. Regular cross-validation checks were conducted by multiple experts to minimize errors and confirm the accuracy of the species identification process. Additionally, any discrepancies in species identification were resolved through expert consultations and, when necessary.

3.9.6.1 Expert Consultations

Throughout the data collection process, expert botanists and ecologists were consulted to validate tree species identification, particularly in cases where species were challenging to distinguish. Experts were available both on-site and remotely to provide guidance and confirm species identification. Expert knowledge involved was as well indigenous from the local people.

3.9.6.2 Data Verification in the Field

During data collection, data collectors cross-verified the accuracy of recorded information, including tree species names, DBH measurements, and geospatial coordinates. In cases of discrepancy, the data was corrected on the spot and further verification was sought.

3.9.6.3 Data Entry and Validation

Data collected in the socioeconomic field were entered using a deployed kobo-collect collection tool connected to a server, and tree data with notebooks. Kobo toolbox was used because it could allow for data collection while offline and is both cheap and faster for the respondent's answers. This was done with double-entry procedures. Data entry was performed by separate individuals, and data validation checks were conducted to identify and rectify any discrepancies between entries.

3.9.6.4 GPS Accuracy and Consistency

The Germin (GPSmap 62st) and smart phone Global Positioning System (GPS) devices was used to record study plot's locations calibrated and cross-checked for accuracy and consistency. Data collectors were trained to minimize GPS-related errors, such as signal interference and imprecise coordinates during ground truthing.

3.9.7 Ethical Considerations

The tree inventory process, and measuring of the study plots process adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring minimal disruption to the ecosystem. My fellow researchers and I took measures to minimize environmental impact and prevent harm to the trees during the tagging and data collection process. Additionally, all necessary permits and approvals were obtained to conduct fieldwork within the study areas (plots where LULC changes occurred), adhering to legal and ethical standards for environmental research. Free Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC) from all stakeholders was a must during data collection in all areas of study to avoid community backlash, conflicts, and resistance during especially the measurement of the 50m-by-50m plots. This was imperative because majority of the locals think of land grabbing by the rich men kind of propaganda.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Demographic characteristics of respondents.

Questionnaires were used in collecting baseline data and respondents of various age brackets were interviewed in accordance with the research study which consisted of 50 respondents from 50 households. The households were in the different study plots of interest where LULC changes occurred for land conditions including improved, stable, and degraded.

Socioeconomic survey

4.1.1 Length of stay in the catchment area

Figure 7. Showing the count of length of stay in the catchment area by respondents

Figure 6 shows that 45 respondents from 45 different households that is 90% of the total respondents have lived in the catchment area for over 10 years as compared to 10% that represents less than 10 years. This makes the collected data reliable and robust. The longer the stay, the better the observations of different LULC changes in a given area by the respondents.

4.1.2 Age distribution of respondents

Figure 8. showing age of respondents in the area

Figure 7 indicates that most of the respondents were in the age range of 18-25 years which is 32% followed by 68% who lie in other age brackets. The older ones have as well stayed in the catchment area for over the last 10 years therefore have gained enough knowledge about the dynamics of different tree species and their occurrence.

4.1.3 Gender distribution of respondents

Gender equity was taken into account to minimize bias and thus both men and women were included in the target respondents from the different households.

Figure 9. showing the gender distribution of respondents.

Figure 8 shows that most of the respondents were men though relatively a minimal difference to women (gender balance). Males were 54% and females were 46%. More men were involved more in LULC change activities that have influenced tree occurrence and diversity like sand mining, charcoal burning, construction, tree growing, sugarcane growing among others.

4.1.4 Occupation of respondents

Figure 10. showing the occupation level of respondents

Figure 9 shows that most respondents are farmers with a percentages of 56% and followed by 'other' with 32% represented by 16 by count. The others consisted mainly of business owners

e.g., Retailers and small traders and the jobless. Some respondents emphasized the lack of jobs being the main reason for tree cutting for charcoal burning for survival. The students had good knowledge on tree conservation as compared to the fishers, some famers and other groups.

4.1.5 Income levels of respondents

Figure 11. showing the income levels of respondents

Figure 10 indicates that most of the respondents 76% earn below 100,000 Ugshs (Uganda shillings), 4% earn above 500,000 Ugshs per month. These low-income levels are attributed to drivers of LULC changes that negatively affect tree occurrence and diversity in Nalwekomba wetland catchment. Such human induced activities were proven by respondents' responses which included, charcoal burning, firewood, and timber for money.

4.2 Impacts of Land Use Land Cover Changes in the Catchment Area

4.2.1. LULC change detection from 2013 - 2021

Figure 12 showing classified Landsat 8 images of LULC changes in Nalwekomba wetland Catchment 2013

Figure 13 showing classified Landsat 8 images of LULC changes in Nalwekomba wetland Catchment 2021

Table 3. showing land conditions and the sum of area change from (2013 to 2021) in Hectares

Land Condition	Sum of Area Change (Ha)	%age Area Change
Degraded	4502.914282	20.83
Improved	3693.308425	17.09
Stable	13417.80723	62.08
Grand Total	21614.02993	100

Table 3 above shows results from the LULC change detection indicates that changes in LULC in the 21614.03 Ha (216.14 Km²) Nalwekomba catchment, consists of: 562.86 Ha/yr. are degraded which is 20.83%, 462.66 Ha/yr. are Improved which is 17.09%, and 1,677.23 Ha/yr. are stable which is 62.08% of the total area.

Figure 14. showing the Count of Change Detection (2013 - 2021) by Land Condition

Figure 13 above indicates Degraded with the most frequency 15, which is 50% of the LULC changes in the catchment, 10 on count for Improved land condition which is 33.3% and on count 5 for stable land condition which is 16.7% as a result of continued human activities in the catchment area for 8 years from year 2013 to 2021

Table 4. showing LULC and sum of their area by 2013

LULC 2013	Sum of Area 2013 (Ha)	%age Area Change
Agroforestry	54246	42.83
Artificial	9170	7.24
Cropland	6165	4.87
Flooded Vegetation	5226	4.13
Swamp	51852	40.94
Water	0	0.00
Grand Total	126659	100

Table 4 indicates that the classified LULC image for the year 2013 did not have water but the rest of the classes existed including Agroforestry, Artificial, Cropland, Flooded vegetation, and swamp. Agroforestry was the most common land cover with a total area of 54,246 hectares healthy diverse tree species within, and then secondly was the swamp land cover with a total area of 51,852 hectares.

Figure 15 showing the area (Ha) per LULC in 2013

Figure 14 indicates that both Agroforestry and Swamp LULC were over 5000 hectares in 2013, and the rest of the LULC including Artificial, cropland, flooded Vegetation and water were below 1000 hectares. The impact was relatively minimal since Agroforestry cover was way high and it consists of trees/forests and other vegetation.

Table 5. showing LULC and sum of their area by 2021

LULC 2021	Sum of Area 2021 (Ha)	%age Area
Agroforestry	39035	32.77
Artificial	11340	9.52
Cropland	2485	2.52
Flooded Vegetation	1698	1.43
Swamp	64560	54.19
Water	18	0.02
Grand Total	119136	100

Table 5. Comparing the grand total area of the catchment in the year 2013 and 2021, it clearly shown that the catchment total area with existing LULC reduced from 126,659 hectares to 119,136 hectares respectively a significant decrement of 7,523 hectares. This has been as a result of continued human activities that have altered the catchment hydrological regimes over the 8-year interval.

Figure 16 Showing area (Ha) per LULC in 2021

Figure 15 indicates a rapid decrease in Agroforestry by 15,21 hectares from 54,246 hectares due to intense human activities of especially sugarcane growing in the catchment. The swamp area increased by 12,708 hectares due to changes in hydrological regimes and human activities such as sand mining and sugarcane growing together with rice.

Figure 17. Showing %age area change of LULC in 2013 and 2021 respectively.

Figure 16 shows a significant decrease percentage area of the “Agroforestry” LULC from 2013 to 2021 by 42.83% to 32.77% (10.11% decrease). This indicates a negative impact on tree **TOD** in the catchment due to discovered human activities including: tree cutting for charcoal production, construction materials, firewood, sugarcane growing which is congruent to findings by (Gimbo. R et al., 2023), (Asselen, 2013), (Isabirye, 2021), and (Alice Nakiyemba, 2021) review by (Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020).

Table 6. LULC change impact extent on land condition projection based from 2013 – 2021 period

Projection Scenario (Yrs.)	Degraded Land (Ha)	Improved Land (Ha)	Stable Land (Ha)
1 yr.	563.86	462.66	1,677.23

4.3. Tree diversity and Occurrence in the catchment

Stable land Condition under LULC change from Artificial to Agroforestry with existing different tree species abundancy and distribution in the site.

Observed species change over the past years in the catchment area.

Figure 18. showing sum of response count for tree species change observations over the past years in the catchment area.

Figure 17 above shows that majority of the residents from the different households of different parts of the catchment where LULC changes and impacts on tree diversity and occurrence admitted an observation of a decrease in some tree species. That is 92% of the observations observed a decrease and 8% observed an increase in tree species. That 4% increase was from areas where the LULC changes were from Agroforestry to Agroforestry and Cropland to Agroforestry. The 92% represented areas in the catchment where LULC changes mostly including Agroforestry to Artificial and Agroforestry to Cropland.

Site 1: (Artificial to Agroforestry - Improved)

Figure 19 Tree occurrence and diversity under an improved LULC change (Artificial to Agroforestry) in the first site in Nabwingulu

Species richness using the Shannon's ([Shannon Diversity Index Calculator \(omnicalculator.com\)](http://Shannon Diversity Index Calculator (omnicalculator.com)))

Table 7. Showing Tree species and their abundancy (Qty)

Tree Species	Species Abundancy (Qty)
Avocado	2
Gacia	9
Guava	2
Jackfruit	20
Kilara	2
Lemon	1
Mango	9
Mukoko	1
Mulongo	1
Musita	4
Musizi	2
Mutuba	3
Muvule	1
Muziru	1
Papaya	2
Grand Total	60

Shannon diversity index = 2.17

Evenness = 0.803

Richness (number of species) = 15

Total number of individuals = 60

Average population size = 4

Site 2: (Cropland to Agroforestry - Improved)

Site 2 of LULC change from Agroforestry is an improved land condition since tree are intermixed with crops. The two interact symbiotically to benefit and thus improved soils and high occurrence of trees and diversity is attributed to such LULC changes from cropland to Agroforestry.

Figure 20 A graph showing the Sum of tree species abundancy against names of tree species for an improved site (LULC change from Cropland to Agroforestry)

Figure 19 shows the sum of tree species abundancy against names of tree species for an improved site (LULC change from Cropland to Agroforestry). The LULC change from cropland to Agroforestry exhibits a very high occurrence and diversity of tree species in that particular part of the catchment. People have grown so much Eucalyptus, Mukomakoma (local name of a tree species), and Mukunu in the area.

Table 8 showing tree species and their abundancy for 2 sites (of 50m by 50m)

Tree Species	Species Abundancy (Qty)
Eucalyptus	158
Gacia	1
Jackfruit	4
Jambula	1
Kapanka	15
Kasitani	1
Kinazi	3
Kiroowa	3
Lemon	1
Mangada	13
Mango	8
Mufuwanduzi	8
Mukoko	2
Mukomakoma	22
Mukunu	26
Mululuza	5
Munalika	4
Musambamaadi	2
Musambya	4
Musita	10
Musizi	7
Musuni	1
Musuuni	2
Muvule	4
Muwa	5
Muyirigiti	1
Grand Total	311

From **Table 8** above;

Shannon diversity index = 2.05 (the index value suggests a moderate level of diversity)

Evenness = 0.637 (the tree species in the study area are relatively evenly distributed)

Richness (number of species) = 25 (a richness value of 25 suggests a relatively diverse tree community)

Total number of individuals = 311

Average population size = 12.4

Site 1 (Agroforestry to Artificial - Degraded)

Site 1 of the Degraded land Condition under LULC change from Agroforestry to Artificial with existing different tree species abundance and distribution in the site.

Figure 21 A graph showing Sum of tree species abundance against size and name of tree species of a degraded site (Agroforestry to Artificial LULC change)

Figure 20 above shows the relatively stable land Condition under LULC change from Agroforestry to Agroforestry with existing different tree species abundance and distribution in the site. Also, the high number of small sized trees on the extreme right of the graph (*Figure 20*) indicates that trees were just of recently grown and very few medium size trees since they are ones most used for firewood and construction of small local houses.

Table 9. showing tree species and their abundancy of a single degraded site (50m by 50m)

Tree Species	Species Abundancy (Qty)
Avocado	1
Gacia	1
Jackfruit	5
Jakaranda	1
Kirowa	1
Lemon	2
Mango	9
Mukoko	1
Musambya	12
Musita	2
Musizi	1
Mutuba	7
Muvule	3
Papaya	4
Grand Total	50

From **Table 9** above:

Shannon diversity index = 2.25

Evenness = 0.854

Richness (number of species) = 14

Total number of individuals = 50

Average population size = 3.57

Site 1 (Agroforestry to Agroforestry - Stable)

Site 1 of the stable land conditions from Agroforestry to Agroforestry indicate no significant impact of human induced activities on the catchment. Therefore, this form of LULC change has a negligible impact on tree occurrence and diversity in that particular area within the catchment.

Figure 22. Showing the sum of tree species and the sum of their abundancy under (Agroforestry to Agroforestry) 2013-2021.

Figure 21 shows that since 2013 to 2021 pines and eucalyptus (*Grandis*) which are new species (not indigenous) have been the mostly planted trees that both make a small forest in that given area. However, there existed a few other tree species in that same area such as muwa, and new Gacia. In summary, it was observed that where existed pines and eucalyptus existed few indigenous tree species.

Table 10. showing tree species and their abundancy of a stable site (Agroforestry to Agroforestry)

Tree Species	Species Abundancy (Qty)
Eucalyptus	211
Gacia	63
Jackfruit	2
Jambula	0
Kapanka	0
Kasitani	0
Kinazi	0
Kiroowa	15
Lemon	0
Mangada	0
Mango	11
Mufuwanduzi	1
Mukoko	0
Mukomakoma	8
Mukooge	1
Mukunu	0
Mululuza	0
Munalika	1
Musambamaadi	0
Musambya	2
Musita	15
Musizi	0
Musuni	0
Musuuni	0
Mutuba	2
Muvule	0
Muwa	14
Muyirigiti	0
Neem	0
Orange	1
Pine	224
Grand Total	571

From table 20 above:

Shannon diversity index = 1.5

Evenness = 0.554

Richness (number of species) = 15

Total number of individuals = 571

Average population size = 38.1

Figure 23. showing Tree species against Sum of size (small, medium, big). (Part of Figure 0-4 above)

Figure 24. showing observed LULC changes affecting tree occurrence and diversity in the catchment area.

Figure 23 shows the respondents' observed LULC changes affecting tree occurrence and diversity in the wetland catchment over the past years agriculture and deforestation are the major LULC that have impacted TOD in the catchment area. This finding is congruent to studies by (Gimbo. R et al., 2023; Bai, Y., Wu, J., & Xing, Q, 2008), and (Justine Kilama Luwa, 2020). Agriculture especially sugarcane growing which whose findings emphasized

4.4. Conservation efforts taken to enhance tree diversity and occurrence in the catchment area.

It is imperative to take conservation efforts to minimize the impacts of LULC changes attributed to human activities so as to enhance the level of tree occurrence and diversity in Nalwekomba catchment area.

Figure 25. Showing the sum of response count towards taking conservation actions on TOD

However, **figure 24** above indicates while 84% of the respondents (from a sample of 50 households) could take action towards conservation practices to enhance tree occurrence and diversity, 16% of the population of respondents from different household did not take action towards conservation of the wetland catchment to enhance tree species diversity and occurrence. 16% of the respondents claimed: not to have enough land to plant any trees (mostly said), not to have seedlings, and poverty.

Also, findings showed that Muvule, Mutuba, and Musita were the less common tree species and eucalyptus, Musizi, Gacia, pine have been more common over the past years in the catchment. Among fruit trees, less common species were oranges, mangoes, and jackfruit among others.

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Summary

The purpose of this study was to assess the impacts of LULC changes on tree diversity and occurrence in Nalwekomba wetland catchment in Kamuli district, Uganda. The study adopted the quantitative and qualitative research methods. Data on trees and from respondents was collected from within the catchment especially where LULC changes occurred. A total of 50 respondents from the 50 households. The study employed a combination of remote sensing, vegetation surveys, and socioeconomic surveys to gather data.

The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining remote sensing data analysis, vegetation surveys, and socioeconomic surveys to gather information on land use and land cover changes, tree diversity, and the perceptions and practices of the local community. The research findings shed light on the current state of tree diversity and occurrence in the catchment area and the factors contributing to land use changes.

5.2. The LULC change detection of the catchment

Figure 26. Showing the sum of area change by land condition from 2013 to 2021.

Table 11 shows the specific LULC changes and impact on the general state of tree diversity and occurrence

Land Condition	Degraded	Improved	Stable
LULC Change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroforestry to Artificial • Agroforestry to Cropland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cropland to Agroforestry • Artificial to Agroforestry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroforestry to Agroforestry

Degraded land conditions comprised of the specific LULC changes that had a detrimental impact on tree occurrence and diversity as shown in *table 11* above. This applied to the improved and stable land conditions. Similarly, (chapter four), **figure 13 and figure 27** indicated LULC change detection with which Degraded (by land condition) had the most frequency 15, which was 50% of the LULC changes in the catchment, 10 on count for Improved land condition which was 33.3% and on count 5 for stable land condition which was 16.7% as a result of continued human activities in the catchment area for 8 years from year 2013 to 2021.

5.3. Tree occurrence and diversity in the catchment area

5.4. Impacts of LULC changes on tree occurrence and diversity in the catchment.

The hypothesis that impacts of tree occurrence and diversity depends of human activities in the catchment area is true.

5.4.1. Artificial to Agroforestry

This LULC change in the site was part of the improved land conditions with a Shannon index of 2.17, species richness of 15 and an evenness of 0.803. this LULC change improved the diversity and occurrence of trees in over eight-year interval as compared to Agroforestry to Artificial LULC change.

5.4.2. Agroforestry to Artificial

This degraded LULC change had a detrimental impact on tree occurrence and diversity in the catchment with a Shannon index of 2.25, species richness of 14 and an evenness of 0.854. this was due to cutting down of trees for timber, firewood, charcoal burning, construction materials and sand mining in the catchment.

5.4.3. Cropland to Agroforestry

As compared to the rest (LULC Changes), it was found out that this improved LULC change from cropland to agroforestry greatly improved tree diversity and occurrence in all areas the

change existed with a diversity index of 2.05 with over 25 tree species richness and 0.637 evenness.

5.4.4. Agroforestry to Agroforestry

This stable LULC change had the least Shannon's index of 1.5 with a species richness value of 15 and an evenness of 0.554. this LULC change reduces occurrence and diversity of other tree species due to the resultant changes in soil types and community tree species especially introduction of eucalyptus and pine trees.

5.5. Limitations of the study

The study focused on a specific geographical area, namely the Nalwenkomba Wetland Catchment in Kamuli District, Eastern Uganda. Therefore, the findings may not be generalized to other regions or ecosystems. Additionally, the research relied on self-reported data from socioeconomic surveys, which may be subject to recall bias or respondent biases. Future studies could consider expanding the scope of the research and employing more robust data collection methods.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. conclusion

From the assessment of LULC changes (from 2013 to 2021) impacts, it is evident that most of the land has been already degraded by human activities especially sugarcane growing, sand mining, tree cutting for charcoal burning, firewood, and timber that have consequently had a significant negative impact on tree diversity and occurrence in Nalwekomba wetland catchment area. The stable land conditions exhibited LULC changes specifically from Agroforestry to Agroforestry which limited the diversity of some species. However, findings indicated that LULC changes in especially improved land conditions from cropland to agroforestry greatly improved the diversity and occurrence of trees species in the catchment area. Therefore, integration of crops with tree growing shall greatly improve the diversity of trees and their occurrence in the catchment area.

6.2. Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are suggested:

Strengthen conservation efforts: It is essential to raise awareness among local communities about the importance of preserving especially fruit trees e.g., mangoes, papaws, oranges, jackfruit among others, and indigenous tree diversity e.g., *Mutuba* (*Mutuba* had numerous uses to the locals such as fodder for animals, leaves for manure in gardens and could grow easily with little care as compared other species), *Musambya*, *Gacia* and implementing sustainable land management practices. This can be achieved through education and community engagement programs after all 84% are already taking action.

Promote sustainable land use practices: Encouraging sustainable agriculture techniques, promoting crops combined with trees (more agroforestry) with specific planting of fruit trees and indigenous tree species like *Mutuba* rather than eucalyptus and pine since it was found that few diverse species existed in places where eucalyptus and pines were grown (Planted forests).

Regulating: especially sugarcane growing and sand extraction activities in the catchment area can help mitigate the negative impacts of land use changes on tree occurrence and regulating new tree species growing (e.g. pines and eucalyptus) for the case of tree diversity.

Enhance community participation: Engaging local communities in decision-making processes and involving them in the design and implementation of conservation initiatives can foster a sense of ownership and responsibility towards the preservation of the wetland catchment area.

Conduct further research: To better understand the long-term impacts of climate change on tree diversity and occurrence, additional research should be undertaken. This research could focus on assessing the vulnerability of different tree species to climate change and identifying suitable adaptation strategies.

Incorporate ecosystem-based approaches: Implementing ecosystem-based approaches in land management planning can help maintain the ecological integrity of the wetland catchment area. This includes considering the interconnectedness of various ecosystem components and promoting sustainable practices that benefit both human communities and the environment.

Collaboration and partnership: Foster collaboration between different stakeholders, including government agencies, research institutions, non-governmental organizations, and local communities. This collaborative approach can facilitate the exchange of knowledge, resources, and expertise, leading to more effective conservation measures.

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APPENDIX 1

Figure 28. 1st photo showing cropland to Agroforestry taken from site 2

Figure 27. 2nd photo showing cropland to Agroforestry taken from site 2

Figure 30. Tree planting in gardens by some farmers (Conservation initiative taken)

Figure 29. Trees used as construction material for local houses

Figure 31 during socioeconomic survey (filling the questionnaires)

APPENDIX 2
QUESTIONNAIRE

Serial No: ...

Dear respondent, I **Odongo Ivan**, a student of Busitema University, Namasagali Campus pursuing a bachelor degree in Natural Resource Economics. The course requires me to write a research report on any relevant topic. My research topic is “*Assessing the Land Use Land Cover Changes on Tree Occurrence and Diversity in Nalwenkomba Wetland Catchment in Kamuli District*”

Your response will provide data for **strictly academic purposes** and shall therefore be kept **confidential**.

Your responses will also contribute to our research on the impacts of land use and land cover changes on tree diversity in the Nalwenkomba wetland. Please answer the following questions to the best of your knowledge.

SECTION 1: DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

1.1 How long have you been in the catchment area?

- a) 1 -5 years
- b) 6 – 10 years
- c) More than 10 years

1.2. Age

- a) 18-25
- b) 26-40
- c) 41-60
- d) 61 and above

1.3. Gender

- a) Male
- b) Female

1.4. Occupation

- a) Farmer

- b) Fisher
- c) Student
- d) Government employee
- e) Other (please specify)

1.5 Income Level

- a) <100,000
- b) 100,000 – 200,000
- c) 300,000 – 400,000
- d) >500,000

SECTION 2: LAND USE AND LAND COVER CHANGES

2.1. Have you noticed any changes in the land use land cover (LULC) in your area over the past years?

- a) Yes
- b) No

2.2. If yes, please briefly specify the types of LULC changes you have observed. You can select multiple options.

- a) Deforestation
- b) Urbanization/infrastructure development
- c) Agriculture (sugarcane, rice, maize)
- d) Wetland restoration
- e) Others (please specify)

SECTION 3: TREE DIVERSITY AND OCCURRENCE & IMPACT

3.1. Do you think there has been a change in the number of tree species within your area in the recent years?

- a) Yes, an increase
- b) No, a decrease
- c) No change
- d) Not sure

3.2. Have you noticed any specific tree species that have become more or less common in your area?

- a) Yes
- b) No

3.3. If yes, please list the tree species that have become MORE common

.....
.....

3.4. If yes, please list the tree species that have become LESS common

.....
.....

3.5. Do you believe that the observed LULC changes have had an impact on tree diversity and occurrence within your area?

- a) Yes, a positive impact
- b) Yes, a negative impact
- c) No impact
- d) Not sure

3.6. If you believe there has been a positive or negative impact, please briefly describe your observations.....

.....

SECTION 4: PERCEPTION OF WETLAND CONSERVATION

4.1. are you involved in any activities related to conserving tree diversity and occurrence within your area?

- a) Yes
- b) No

4.2. If yes please briefly describe the activities you are involved in

.....
.....

SECTION 5: ADDITIONAL COMMENTS

5.1. Do you have any additional comments or suggestions related to land use, tree diversity, or wetland conservation in the Nalwenkomba area?

.....
.....

5.2. Is there any additional information or observations you would like to share regarding the impacts of LULC changes on tree diversity in Nalwenkomba Wetland?

.....
.....

CONCLUSION

Thank you for your valuable input. Your responses will contribute to a better understanding of the complex interactions between human activities, land cover changes, and tree dynamics in the Nalwenkomba Wetland Catchment.